

D6.2 CRITICAL MAKING EVALUATION REPORT

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CAD	Computer-aided design
CMRF	Critical Making Responsibility Framework
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V., Germany
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
PAR	Participatory Action Research
R&I	Research & Innovation
RDI	Research, design & innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
STEM	Science, technology, engineering and mathematics
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package
WP1	Project Management
WP2	Building the critical making knowledge-base: concept & methods
WP3	Case Action: GENDER
WP4	Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS
WP5	Case Action: OPENNESS
WP6	Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications
WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Critical Making project has studied the social responsibility of making and explored together with makers new ways to foster gender inclusion, engagement of young people and openness of making. The project design is based on participatory research methods and a reflexive-interventionist research approach. We have engaged makers throughout the project to co-design the case interventions and co-create the project results. Our particular aim has been to engage people who are often underrepresented both in making and research collaboration, including women and caretakers, people from resource-scarce communities and makers from the global south. Following from that, the evaluation of the responsibility of our own project activities has been essential throughout the project implementation. Furthermore, one of the key aims of our interventionist-reflexive approach is to produce results that are both academically robust and meaningful for the maker communities and thus impactful. This evaluation report presents the results of the evaluation of Critical Making activities first from the point of view of responsibility (RRI) and then explores the impact pathways of project activities.

Most of the frameworks developed to investigate responsibility in research and innovations (RRI) fail to grasp the particularities of grassroots innovations. To respect the principle of two-way learning between the Critical Making researchers and the maker community, we evaluated our research practices with the Critical Making reflection tool that is based on the sustainable making principles originally developed bottom up by the GIG maker community and further elaborated for a reflection tool during the Critical Making project. Although not initially designed for research purposes, it fits well for Critical Making as the project aims to concretely contribute to more responsible making. The tool introduces five dimensions of social responsibility to be evaluated: 1: Integrate local knowledge, 2: Make Things That Make Sense, 3: Share How you Make, 4: Build for Continuity and 5: Include Ecosystem Services. The evaluation indicates that Critical Making succeeded well in dimensions 1-3 which relate to engaging makers in co-designing and co-creation, responding to the needs of maker community to produce results that are relevant for makers and to share them in multiple formats through multiple channels in order to make them accessible for the community of makers. We also managed to engage often underrepresented and even marginalised groups such as people living in refugee camps or women from the communities

of global south into collaboration and offer them support to elaborate bottom up their own projects, while at the same time gaining valuable insights for research. This was due to systematically applied co-design, co-budgeting and co-creation approaches in all the case actions as well as in the elaboration of the conceptual Critical Making Responsibility Framework from theoretical tool to an online game tailored for makers. The project also made attempts to build for continuity (Dimension 3) by acting with existing maker networks such as GIG and Wikifactory which continue to use and share the project outcomes after the end of the project. With regards to including ecosystems, the project performance was not as strong as with the dimensions of social responsibility despite several measures to support environmental sustainability, including support for the projects aiming to solve the problems caused by resource scarcity or environmental pollution for example.

The impact pathways of Critical Making were evaluated with regards to the six impact goals that were specified by the consortium after the first phase of the project. These were: **To support the critical making community creation, To promote inclusiveness in making, To promote critical making education, To promote openness in making, and Raising awareness of critical making.** Similarly, to the responsibility evaluation results, our impact evaluation indicates that Critical Making has succeeded to run impactful activities and produce results which have been relevant and well received in the maker community due to the systematic co-design and co-creation approach. For example, we have managed to promote the awareness of critical making and diversity of voices heard within the making community with inspirational stories and active participation in different forums of discussion. Furthermore, we have provided concrete guidelines for inclusive making, critical making education, openness in making and responsibility evaluation. Our evaluation also shows that our case actions have contributed to upskilling among the people engaged in WP3 interventions and mentoring programme and that way had an empowering impact, both in terms of livelihood and agency within the community. In addition, practical impacts, the academic results of the project have received good response. For example, a paper presenting the Critical Making Responsibility Framework in the FAB17 conference in 2022 won the best paper award. Due to the short project period of 2,5 years, the last research articles on the openness and community engagement dimensions of RRI are still in process during the writing of this

evaluation report. The results of the project provide an excellent basis to continue contributing with these results to the academic RRI discussions.

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE EVALUATION PROCESS

This report presents an overview of the evaluation practices and results of the Critical making project. First, we will introduce the core principles of our evaluation approach, then describe how we organized self-reflection and collection of feedback. After that we will move on to a brief summary of case action activities and evaluate these practices with the use of five responsibility dimensions elaborated in the Critical Making Reflection tool. In the final section, we will have a closer look on the impact pathways that the project outcomes have contributed to.

1.1 Co-evaluation

The Critical Making project design is based on participatory research methods and a reflexive-interventionist research approach. The aim of the project has been to critically investigate the social responsibility of innovation actions within the maker community. Furthermore, the project has aimed to co-design and pilot measures to promote gender sensitivity and inclusion in making, the engagement of young people in making and openness and open hardware. According to our participatory research approach, also the specific goals of the three thematic case intervention work packages (WP3 Gender, WP4 Engagement of Young people, WP5 Openness) were specified in collaboration between the members of the research consortium and the stakeholders engaged in our project practices as described in the baseline report D2.1 and evaluation framework D6.1. Also, the elaboration of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework (CMRF), which outlines the conceptual basis of the project has been further elaborated with a range of engaged practitioners. Following from our genuinely participatory research design, we have also chosen to apply methods of co-evaluation (Schäfer et al. 2021) in collecting feedback and reflecting the success and impacts of our project activities as described in the Critical making evaluation framework (D6.1). This choice has given more power also to our stakeholders as co-researchers to contribute to the contents and direction of research at the course of the project activities.

Because the three case action work packages target partly different audiences and have different goals and engagement methods, the actual evaluation methods also differ, ranging from surveys (WP5), focus-group or expert interviews (WP3, WP4, WP5) and participant observations (WP3, WP4) to collection of feedback in group discussions and for open feedback posters during events (WP4). The more detailed description of methods used are found on the case action reports (D3.2, D4.2, D5.2). The diversity of evaluation methods was also important due to the heterogeneity of the citizen groups engaged in the case actions with varying socio-economic backgrounds, capabilities and resources to participate. Therefore, an integral part of the project evaluation was the reflection of how to organize co-evaluation in each of the case actions in a context-sensitive way. This was particularly relevant with the WP3 case actions which in major part were conducted by the engaged maker communities (see D3.2.).

1.2. Self-reflection

In addition to the co-evaluation practices, the Critical Making consortium members used various self-reflection methods at different phases of the project to discuss the used methods, potential ethical issues encountered and whether there was a need to revise the research approach or aimed goals. These self-reflection methods included:

- meetings of the evaluation group, which consisted of the consortium members that were responsible of case action evaluations in each of the work packages, consortium leader and leader of the evaluation work package
- impact narratives, which were written in two consortium meetings (Vienna May 2023, Berlin October 2023) and building of Critical making future impact pathways in the last consortium meeting on-line in April 2023. The impact narratives were written for each case action with a focus on reflecting how well the project was proceeding towards the impacts we wanted to reach and whether there was a need to revise the approach. An example of impact narratives is in the figure 1 below and the data collection for the impact pathways in figure 2. The future impact pathways are described in more detail in section 3.

What is the impact you aim to achieve with the case actions? Who do you want to influence, what is different afterwards? Write a few sentences.

• influence maker - publish something

With the CM mentoring we want to influence makers to increase the openness of their project and the sustainability of their making overall. (as part of a wider ecosystem of OTH makers we do this through guided self-reflection, training, peer-exchange and incentive for documentation)

Beyond the makers directly participating we share our results and learnings with makerspace managers and community multipliers as a has to for making, making more sustainable. Contribute to landscape of open hardware making, adding sustainability to the teaching, increased academic understanding of sustainable, critical making + openness is further a goal.

How will you know whether you have achieved the desired impact? Write a few sentences.

We get and analyse feedback from participants. Through the self-reflection in the beginning and at the end of the programme and its visual representation we see potential changes in confidence about maker's skills and incorporation of sustainability practices.

Our tool is used by many people outside of the mentoring itself - and also the how-to materials will be useful for people, we will see numbers of people watching the v downloading the how-to, and then get feedback from them.

We're adding to an existing trend and necessity in society to become more sustainable.

We measure the reach and interaction with documented projects from participants and also how hashtags associated with sustainable making are increasing on the WF platform in the last year of CM project.

What have you done this far in your WP to achieve the desired impacts? Write a few sentences.

We have reached out to different open hardware associations and makerspace communities and involved them + informed them about our work. WF has started the work of modifying the community strategy, also informed through participation in the CM project.

Through the co-design and recruitment of jury + teachers we already reached and got commitment from makers, makerspace managers and community multipliers.

We've done the base work and preparation through developing the tool, publishing a peer-reviewed article and adapted our work plan according to the results.

We prepared the platform for sharing documentation and community exchange.

Figure 1: Impact narrative sheet

Figure 2: Example of data collection for the impact pathways

1. EVALUATION WITH THE CRITICAL MAKING REFLECTION TOOL

Following the methodologies of participatory action research (PAR, see e.g. Kindon et al. 2009) the research design of the Critical making project activities has aimed to facilitate dialogue between academic researchers and makers and knowledge exchange and ideation within the maker community. Furthermore, with a bottom up approach for designing the pilots for inclusive making, open hardware mentoring and critical making education, we wanted to engage a broad range of expertise in designing the interventions and to ensure that the solutions were grounded to the varying contexts of interventions. And finally, we believe that a participatory approach is needed to make the research results more inclusive and relevant for a broader audience. Therefore, in addition to case action interventions, we also engaged the international community of makers to elaborate with us the reflection questions of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework and Critical Making online game. This engagement was made through online workshops and surveys. The table 1 provides an overview of the diversity of actors engaged in Critical Making case actions both in terms of demographic factors and geographically.

WP 3: Gender inclusive making		
Type of activity	Geographical coverage	Addressees
Co-design workshops for case interventions Collaborative caretaker-children settings, Project X MakerWomen Inspirational stories Elaboration and evaluation of the Introduction and guidelines for inclusive making Go-Sanitize capacity building workshop Training workshop: empowering women through useful critical making Changes in the online platform to become more gender-inclusive	Austria, Indonesia, Poland, Germany, South Sudan, Cameroon, International/ Online,	Caretakers, mothers and children, nonbinary persons, general public People not yet part of maker spaces and marginalised in dominant maker space cultures Makers and makerspaces that would like to become more inclusive Female brewers involved in Go-Sanitize production Secondary school girls, women in academia, women in rural areas All users of the Wikifactory platform

WP 4: Critical youth maker encounters		
re:publica festival, Mobile makerspace network meeting, Open workshop day at Goodlab, Minute bracamp network meeting of STEM educators, Bildung, Bits un Baume festival delegation and sustainability in education	Main focus in Germany, International maker community during the re:publica festival, background interviews and dissemination	International makers & activists, educators, caretakers with children, teachers, school classes
WP 5: Critical making open hardware programme		
Critical making mentoring programme	Europe, Latin America, Africa	Experienced makers willing to create an SDG impact and get support in open hardware Makers from rural Africa and Latin America Makers living in African refugee camps International community of makerspace leaders and makers
WP 2: Critical Making Responsibility framework		
Critical making responsibility framework Critical making online game for makers	International maker community / online	Experienced makers from Latin America, Asia & Europe engaged for the feedback and co-design of the CMRF framework reflection questions and critical making game

Table 1: Activities of critical making case actions and engaged actors

As emphasised in the literature of participatory research methodologies (eg. Kindon et al. 2009, Wiarda et al. 2023), collaborative research settings need to be designed carefully to allow safe and equal space for communication for actors with different demographic backgrounds, resources for participation and expectations for the project. The table 1 shows that many of the actors engaged in Critical making activities present groups that are often underrepresented in both making and research collaboration, which made it even more important to continuously reflect on the responsibility of the research design and outcomes. For this reason, throughout all the project actions, local activities were supported and new initiatives were always set up so that the local actors held the power over them as much as possible. During our evaluation group meetings, we for example discussed about the importance of the ability to completely run the WP3 case actions with the local languages. Furthermore, we reflected on how to tackle the

power issues often arising in citizen engagement and collaborative research setting between the research team and engaged citizens (see, e.g. Paleco et al. 2021). An example of this is the particular care of making it clear during the Critical Making mentoring programme entry and exit interviews for the mentees that the financial support from the project was not in any way dependent on the feedback they gave us during the group discussions. They were selected for the programme, because of the value of their projects and the support decision was already made. The mentors of the programme were also all selected from Global South countries in order to avoid Eurocentric and neocolonialistic knowledge transfer and instead allow Global South actors to get visibility through the programme.

Different approaches and frameworks to investigate responsibility in research and innovations (RRI) have been developed in increasing numbers during the last decades. However, these frameworks often fail to grasp the particularities of grassroots innovations, which occur outside the institutionalised R&D organisations such as maker spaces. According to our background studies conducted for the evaluation framework, the existing RRI approaches for example largely miss the importance of community engagement and empowerment as one evaluation criteria (see D6.1. & Sipos et al. 2021, Saari et al. 2023, pdf in annex). However, the importance of community impacts is well recognised in the responsibility principles originating from the community of makers themselves. To respect the principle of two-way learning between the Critical Making researchers and the maker community, we will in the following evaluate our research practices with the Critical Making reflection tool that is based on the sustainable making principles originally developed bottom up by the GIG maker community and further elaborated for a reflection tool during the Critical Making project (see D2.2, D6.3).

Critical Making reflection tool has been tested, used and elaborated in several maker encounters during the project and it was also used in WP5 as a self-evaluation tool for the mentoring programme participants. According to the mentees, the tool was very useful for them to gain new perspectives to their own work, identifying the strengths and development points of their project in terms of social and environmental impacts. Although the tool is not initially developed to evaluate research projects, we find it useful for reflecting the responsibility of Critical Making activities, as the tool reflects many of the principles of responsible

citizen engagement (eg. respect local knowledge, accessible and fair sharing of results, paying attention to the community impacts of activities etc.) and it is particularly designed to address the context of making. The tool introduces five different dimensions of responsible making and provides them with an evaluation scale. In the following, we will reflect our actions per each of these dimensions.

Integrate local knowledge: *Integration of local knowledge requires listening, collaboration and shared decision making. It is valuable in building an impactful, fair and inclusive project that genuinely brings value to its participants. Integration of local knowledge can be seen as an opposite to top-down design of projects. By integrating and utilizing local knowledge, access to tacit, context-specific understandings can be gained. Integration of local knowledge can be achieved in many ways, for example by co-creation, consultations or by distributing decision making power to local actors.*

Figure 3: Integrate local knowledge, project evaluation.

Integration of local knowledge in the research design and co-creation have been corner stones of Critical Making throughout the project timeline. Thus, in every work package, consulting practitioners, co-designing with them and supporting their pre-existing initiatives have been common practices. According to several studies, citizen engagement in research collaboration and citizen science projects tend to be biased in terms of gender and socio-demographic backgrounds so that for example women and people from lower income groups are underrepresented (e.g. Burgess et al. 2017). We have wanted to take these biases seriously and make an effort to engage also groups underrepresented both in research collaboration and making, such as women, non-binary people, and people living under resource scarcity including for example residents of refugee camps. In addition, Critical Making interventions have engaged people from multiple communities of the Global South living in very diverse contexts. We have recognized the difficulty of creating meaningful and accessible participatory interventions for people from

varying contexts as a completely European consortium. Therefore, we have used co-design methods in all of the work packages creating content for makers. We have also aimed to facilitate peer to peer learning between the makers rather than running interventions by the research team.

One example, which can also serve as a model for further grassroots innovations research projects is the concept of co-design and co-budgeting of the case actions of WP3 described in the D3.2. The suggestions for case actions were developed and selected collaboratively with a group of people from different backgrounds and locations who also made the final decisions of distributing the available budget for the selected pilots in a participatory manner. In this case, the distribution was not even, but based on the needs of each of the actions. In addition to engaging local knowledge to address the needs of the makers when designing and resourcing the interventions, the co-design and co-budgeting also created transparency and ownership for the makers engaged in the project. In addition, the WP3 research team co-writes an article together with the engaged makers to provide ownership also for the academic results of the project to the non-academic co-researchers. In previous citizen science research, engaging people from low-income communities in research without financial compensation or other clear benefits for the community has been frequently criticized (eg. Chan et al. 2017, Cieslik et al. 2019, Resnik et al. 2015). Therefore, we found these co-design and co-budgeting methods particularly crucial for the intervention design.

Also the Critical Making Mentoring programme was co-designed with experienced makers in two online co-design sessions where both the contents and the working methods were planned. The co-design sessions had participants from broad geographical coverage, for example Brazil, Indonesia, Zimbabwe, Canada and UK. In this way, local knowledge from many different contexts was present, which was extremely purposeful as the scope of the mentoring programme was global. In the co-design sessions, things like targeted participant groups, participant experiences and the main outcomes for the participants were discussed. The potential mentors were also discussed in the co-design sessions to get a broad geographical coverage and range of relevant expertise covered. Eventually, all of the selected mentors came from Global South backgrounds. During the mentoring programme care was also taken not to impose our ideas to the participant in a context-insensitive way. Instead, peer learning, learning from examples and equal knowledge exchange were emphasised.

In WP4 activities the targeted communities were mainly the German teachers, educators and makers. Thus, the integration of local knowledge in this case meant engaging with teachers, educators and school classes guided by their teacher to collect knowledge of the barriers and possibilities in integrating critical making into school curricula and to find ways for collaboration between makers and schools. The Critical making manifesto, which is directed to an international audience, is developed based on these encounters and reflects the views of teachers and makers on what critical making means for the educators and how to communicate it.

Even with our commitment to integrating local knowledge and being inclusive in our design, difficulties were also inevitable. The main difficulty that we encountered had to do with popularizing scientific work. One example of this is the Critical Making Responsibility Framework (CMRF) developed in WP2, that aimed at bringing RRI closer to the reality of grass-roots actors in a way that would be useful for them. The framework was for long circulated in the consortium as a matrix of reflexive questions, and the researchers of the project kept coming up with ever so complex reflexive questions for the different aspects of the framework. Eventually, after one and a half years of elaboration inside the consortium a co-creation session with makers was arranged. The co-creative session immediately led to establishing a new direction for the framework, and the online game design was started. For this process, a maker and game designer was engaged. This example illustrates the difficulty of creating popularised tools as academic researchers, and the need to engage practitioners when designing tools for them.

Another example of a failure in meeting the realities of makers was our attempt to respond to the wishes of the mentoring programme participants of WP5 to increase their understanding of how they can evaluate and show their SDG impacts. In the application phase, the applicants were asked to choose the SDGs that their project contributed towards. Despite being able to choose 1-4 SDGs for their application, many told during the entry interviews that they found the SDG framework difficult and expressed their willingness to learn more about it. To respond to this request, we decided to hold an SDG training tailored for the mentoring programme participants as an unofficial extra session of the programme. We decided also to explore the possibility of creating an SDG tool for

makers that would help them more efficiently and precisely describe their projects' contributions towards the SDGs. In the training session, general background of SDGs was explained, putting them in context. We also provided the makers with some general recommendations on reporting the SDG impacts of their projects (see the slides of training in Annex). After this general training session, we also provided the participants with a set of questions that aimed at helping them reflect on the SDG impacts of their projects and offered a session to reflect on the questions and go through their thoughts on the SDG exercise together. The questions, which were formulated by two researchers proved to be still too far from the realities of makers and several of them reported having had to use a long time to elaborate their answers. This underlined again the importance of co-design which had been neglected while preparing the set of questions. Despite this failure, many participants expressed their happiness with the training session, as it had increased their understanding of the SDGs and helped them improve their thinking in relation to impact and international goals. Furthermore, during the interactive SDG session, in-depth, insightful discussions emerged, and the participants were able to learn a lot from each other's interpretations of SDG goals. This served again as a reminder for us that making research make sense for non-academics, co-design and co-creation is a necessity.

According to Bonney et al. (2009) integration of multiple voices to research through citizen engagement is not possible without careful background work of getting to know the particular citizen groups and communities that are aimed to be engaged and to identify their motivations and barriers for engagement. The Critical Making project used multiple co-creation methods to engage in our research design and implementation people who belonged to the communities we wanted to work with. For these reasons, and despite of the two drawbacks we have reported here, we have evaluated our performance on the reflection tool to be high on the line of "integrate local knowledge", to "integration of both local knowledge and practices".

Make things that make sense: *Making things that make sense has to do with purposeful design of projects and responsiveness to real community needs. In the context of making, this principle reminds people about the need to not only make for fun or to design things in bubbles but to explore what the real social needs are. On the reflection tool dimensions, the scale goes from "just for fun" to "fundamental, can also*

be fun”, emphasizing the societal value of the projects. With regards to research, just for fun could refer to projects directed completely to academic interests.

Figure 4: *Make things that make sense, project evaluation.*

Citizen science projects have been frequently criticized of engaging people in projects that mainly benefit researchers which creates a risk of exploitation (e.g. Riesch & Potter 2014). The core idea of the Critical Making consortium has been to produce results which support the responsibility of making. Therefore, we have paid particular attention on ensuring that the project outcomes are meaningful for the engaged maker communities. One way to make this happen has been the decision to use project activities as a platform to exchange knowledge within the maker community and elaborate it together with the research team. Furthermore, as described earlier, co-creation and support of makers’ own projects and needs has been very central for the project to ensure that the interventions and project outcomes make sense in the local contexts. For example, all the case actions of WP3 were suggested by local makers from different contexts and thus addressed the very specific needs of different communities ranging from caretaker inclusive making formats to making the Wikifactory platform more gender inclusive.

In addition, the Critical Making consortium has also been prepared to adapt the initial working plan to better suit the needs of engaged makers. One example of such change in the work plan to make more sense for grass-roots practitioners was the creation of an online game based on the Critical Making Responsibility Framework. This framework started as a highly academic exercise with complex questions that were demanding to answer. In this form, the framework received mixed feedback from the makers. On the one hand, it was deemed insightful and interesting, but on the other hand, very impractical to makers, who generally want to use more of their time in making than doing complex written exercises. The idea of producing an online game originated from a co-design session with

makers. As an online game the exercise should be fun rather than worksome, and yet the reflexive questions are there, and new thoughts might arise.

Another example of adapting to make more sense for the practitioners comes from WP4 where educational aspects of critical making were in focus. There, makers were consulted many times about their needs and best ways to implement the project's plans. In the end, one of the outcomes of the work package is a poster that is co-designed with makers in physical events and online consultations. This was deemed by the makers to fulfill the needs of many, as the poster can be hung on a wall of any makerspace or classroom, thus allowing for a wide audience to get familiar with the principles of critical making. As simple as this approach seems, it can thus make a lot of sense in distributing the values of the project further. WP4 activities also brought up one dilemma in promoting critical thinking while trying to make things playful and fun for makers. According to the WP4 feedback, in some workshop sessions aiming to demonstrate critical making methods for educators, the time was spent mostly on making and reflection was downplayed due to time pressure. In these cases, the pressure to make things "maker like" and fun did override the criticality, which is a risk that needs to be considered while developing these methodologies further.

All in all, the Critical Making project has done a lot of work to make its research more useful and adapted to the practical grass-roots communities. Thus, we placed the mark on this dimension on "fundamental, can also be fun", in the very end of the spectrum. A remarkable part of the work of making sense for grass-roots communities has been translating our fundamental ideas into fun, engaging and inclusive practices.

Share how you make: *Sharing how you make points to the value of sharing knowledge openly so that it allows others to exploit your experiences and build upon your work. There are different ways to share, and the sharing practices should also be fitted for the audience you are sharing with. Creating good quality and easily understandable documentations can sometimes be a difficult and time-consuming task, but if it prevents someone from re-inventing the wheel, it is usually worth it. Open sharing is not only about sharing the end results, but also the process of getting there.*

Figure 5: Share how you make, project evaluation.

Open science is one of the six RRI keys and openness of making was one of the selected focus areas of Critical Making. Therefore, open sharing has also been an important value for the Critical Making project from the beginning. A decision has been made early on to share all the deliverables of the project open access through Zotero, which is also linked to the project website as a resource for anyone interested. The project has also been committed to open access publishing and sharing our learnings for academic peers in conferences.

From the beginning, the Critical Making project has put an emphasis on communicating the research outcomes for the grass-roots maker communities as much as possible, in formats that serve them. The Wikifactory platform has been utilized throughout the project as a site of sharing about the project in a popular format. The platform allows sharing stories with images and links, in addition to its core function as a hardware design sharing platform. This allowed us to use it as a platform to tell about events and publications in a popular format. We have also disseminated easy to read and access guidelines for inclusive making and inspirational stories on our project website.

As the project progressed, it started to seem obvious that only sharing reports, Wikifactory posts and social media posts was not enough to reach the grass-roots maker communities. As connecting to the practitioners was important for the Critical Making project, new ways of sharing what we were doing were ideated across work packages. An online game was designed as a popular version of the Critical Making Responsibility Framework. It aimed at both being fun and engaging and initiating new thoughts and discussions. A Critical Making project Zine was also created. It included some information of all of the case action work packages of the project as well as some tools, core values of the project and some key information about the impacts of the project, packaged in a punk-culture style.

Another creative means of dissemination was a Critical Making “Wundertute”, a package including a torch building set with instructions as well as a set of Critical Making guidelines and the Manifesto. This package has an educational backdrop and is especially targeting children and youth. These results were finalised in the final stage of the project timeline, which means that during this evaluation, we have not yet had time to collect broader feedback from the maker community. These efforts however indicate the ability of the research team to respond to makers’ feedback and willingness to address diverse audiences and to learn different methods of making the results interesting and accessible for different groups of people.

The Critical Making project has also encountered difficulties with its outreach and communication which have had an impact on project implementation. One point where the strategy of communication had to be rethought was the Critical Making mentoring programme, where a minimum number of 50 applications was targeted and up to 36 participants would have been admissible for the programme. Instead, the programme received 34 applications, 18 of which were approved. Due to this, we revised our plans to share the contents of the programme and opened parts of the mentoring programme to the outsiders as well, and recorded and added the mentoring sessions to Youtube. The first mentoring sessions already has more than 70 views and the resources will be further shared and used by the GIG and Wikifactory communities and in other projects such as mAKE .

The scale on the reflection tool presented above is not targeted for research but maker projects. That’s why placing the Critical Making project on the line is not straight forward. As we have shared a number of different outcomes of our project, including guidelines for hosting mentoring programmes, hosting inclusive makerspaces as well as critical maker education, we placed Critical Making project on “some instructions”.

Build for continuity: *Build for continuity refers to building for long term practices and securing continuation. Building for continuity has many aspects, such as creating lasting communities that will reproduce the practices. Financial sustainability is also important in securing the continuation of projects and practices, as financial failure often means the end of an endeavor. Therefore, building for continuity includes*

planning for the future - how will one be able to sustain their activities over time and make them resilient in face of challenges?

Figure 6: Build for continuity, project evaluation.

For the Critical Making project, as for any research project, building for continuity is somewhat difficult, as the project is set to last a period of time and end as planned. For the project to have long term impacts some continuity should be created, but the future of any activities is mostly out of the hands of the researchers currently working on the project. Continuity does not thus mean continuing our practices as such, but rather attempts to create a lasting legacy.

To build for long lasting impacts, the Critical Making project has from the start aimed at contributing to existing communities. Global Innovation Gathering (GIG) which is a core partner of the consortium has consistently built a global maker community for long before the project. During the project, this community was engaged through workshops, co-creation actions and invited to participate in project activities, including the mentoring programme and the gender case actions. The Critical Making project has also consistently disseminated its results, events and outputs to the GIG community to give them access to all the resources produced.

In the same manner, the Wikifactory platform has been consistently used throughout the project to document and disseminate the activities. All of the mentees of the Critical Making mentoring programme were directed to Wikifactory, where a Critical Making group page had been created, and encouraged to share documentations about their projects. The community aspect allows continuity, even though it is impossible to say at this point whether long-term sharing practices really will take place. When the mentoring programme was ending, several mentees were receiving contributions to their Wikifactory files and had established connections with each other through further online media as

well. In addition, they now have the skills to use the community platform and dig into the knowledge of the whole wider community.

In the self-reflection tool, we have placed the Critical Making project in the middle of the “build for continuity” line shown above, indicating the “potential for self-sustainability identified”. What is meant by this, is that there are several seeds that could grow into continuous, long-term impacts. Still, instead of a well-defined and coordinated strategy, these seeds will all start to live their separate lives in the hands of the community members and individual project partners.

Integrate ecosystem services: *Integrate ecosystem services can be understood as making environmentally wise decisions. The scale of the reflection tool goes from “toxic” to “giving back more than consuming”, highlighting the different relationships a project can have with its natural surroundings. To have a positive or even harmonious relationship with the natural environment, it is important for a project to think about its use of resources, producing potentially harmful wastes as well as its potential for positive solutions for the environment.*

Figure 7: *Integrate ecosystem services, project evaluation.*

Taking responsibility for the environment has been an important factor for the Critical Making project, even if not the main focus. Making environmentally wise decisions, e.g. making travel plans by plane only when necessary, has organically grown into the working habits of the project.

In WP5 Critical Making mentoring programme environmental sustainability was one of the criteria for the engaged mentoring projects. Furthermore, integrating the ecosystem services formed one of the five themes of mentoring. Even before the last mentoring session covering the ecosystem services, the environmental impacts of projects were the topic of many discussions. The mentees were asked in the application phase to select the most important SDGs that their project contributed for. Even if not all of them chose an environmentally focused SDG, many still felt the need to ponder their environmental impacts. It was evident that

for most mentees the environment was a very important aspect, and during the mentoring many also reported a shift to recycled materials or other environmentally motivated changes in their work. Furthermore, one of the projects directly dealt with developing more environmentally sustainable textiles out of the residues of banana production and some searched for solutions to the management of scarce resources such as irrigation systems for plants in a refugee camp.

While balancing between the environmental burden created by the project activities and the support given for maker projects aiming for ecological impact, we need to situate the Critical Making project in the reflection tool to “giving back less than consumed”. Even though we did take some efforts not to consume too much ecological resources and encouraged the engaged makers to do the same, it is probable that during its lifetime the Critical Making project created more emissions and other environmentally harmful side-effects (due to travels, materials for workshops etc.) than it was able to save through changes in practitioners' practices. As the project had more social than environmental focus, we deem this acceptable, even though of course undesired outcome.

Summary of the Reflection tool evaluation

The figure below summarizes the results of the responsibility evaluation of Critical Making.

Figure 8: Summary of self-reflection

The evaluation indicates that Critical Making succeeded well in dimensions 1-3 which relate to engaging makers in co-designing and co-creation, responding to

the needs of maker community to produce results that are relevant for makers and to share them in multiple formats through multiple channels in order to make them accessible for the community of makers. We also managed to engage often underrepresented and even marginalised groups such as people living in refugee camps or women from the communities of global south into collaboration and offer them support to elaborate bottom up their own projects, while at the same time gaining valuable insights for research. This was due to systematically applied co-design, co-budgeting and co-creation approaches in all the case actions as well as in the elaboration of the conceptual Critical Making Responsibility Framework from theoretical tool to an online game tailored for makers. The project also made attempts to build for continuity (Dimension 3) by acting with existing maker networks such as GIG and Wikifactory which continue to use and share the project outcomes after the end of the project and by supporting through case actions several maker projects that had been already on-going before the project and continue after it (most of the mentoring proejects). With regards to including ecosystems, the project performance was not as strong as with the dimensions of social responsibility despite several measures to support environmental sustainability, including support for the projects aiming to solve the problems caused by resource scarcity or environmental pollution for example.

3. CRITICAL MAKING IMPACT PATHWAYS

In the previous section, we evaluated the responsibility of the Critical Making project activities by using the reflection tool of engaged makers communities. Now, we move on to have a look at the impacts of the project. After the first co-design phase of the Critical making project in October 2022, the consortium elaborated its impact goals and defined the following 5 long-term goals:

1. **To support the Critical Making community creation:** We want to help makers build long-lasting communities and create new contacts, both locally and globally. We want to support current makerspaces in their community building, using their platforms and letting them have their own space. We also wish to create or strengthen communality around critical making among teachers and support the online communities of makers, through e.g. the Wikifactory platform.

2. **To promote inclusiveness in making:** We want to help create a more diverse maker community. We want to consider intersectionality, including gender diversity and socioeconomic backgrounds. We want to support cooperation between the global north and south. We want to consider the practices that exclude certain groups from making. We also want to share this knowledge and understanding into the maker communities we work with.
3. **Critical Making education:** We want to integrate critical making into the education system, both in schools and universities. We also want to educate makers about critical making. Raising makers' reflexivity is a part of this.
4. **Openness:** We work mainly with open hardware, and as a research project we want to be doing our part for open science. Openness work package is especially concerned with this, but other work packages consider these questions as well. We see openness as one of the main pillars of the maker movement.
5. **Raising awareness of critical making:** We want to raise the publics' awareness of critical making. We also want to raise critical making more into the funding schemes of EU.

As frequently noted in the research impact assessment literature, the exact measurement of research impacts is often impossible due to the time lags between the research and its impacts and because the higher-level outcomes are out of the sphere of the influence of one research project only (e.g. Adam et al. 2018 & Belcher & Hughes 2020) This also applies to the impact evaluation of the Critical Making project. As the aimed future goals are mainly characteristically qualitative and relate to slowly developing long-term changes in practices and culture, we have described them in the below table (Table 2) in a qualitative manner and with qualitative evidence of impacts based on our evaluation data. The impact pathways presented in the table are based on the final self-evaluation workshop of the consortium in May 2023, during which we critically reflected how well the consortium had managed to contribute to these goals and explored observed evidence of impact. The more detailed quantitative data about the project outreach and KPIs is found in the dissemination and exploitation report (D7.3).

GOAL: COMMUNITY CREATION

OUTCOMES OF RESEARCH	EXPECTED IMPACT PATHWAY	IDENTIFIED IMPACT
<p>Joint co-creation events in all the work packages</p> <p>Visibility for maker projects in Wikifactory (WP5)</p> <p>Support of different maker communities to address gender diversity in making (WP3)</p> <p>Network building within the mentoring programme mentees and mentors (WP5)</p>	<p>The Critical Making consortium wanted to use participatory research methods to support and facilitate the local maker communities and global maker networks in strengthening and building their own communities in the long-run. We expected that the communities engaged in critical making consider the insights from the process and nourish and spread them in their every-day life</p> <p>We actively facilitated discussions of critical making in existing maker communities and events to engage more people in the community</p> <p>The Wikifactory platform was used to facilitate easy to access on-line exchange of knowledge, ideas and insights</p>	<p>The active participation in the Critical Making Manifesto statement collection during re:publica 2022 and 2023 showed increasing interest in critical making within the maker community</p> <p>During the exit and entry interviews of Mentoring Programme, the participants highlighted the importance of the connections created for the broader maker community to support their own projects</p> <p>The involvement of different makerspaces and makers in the gender activities created well perceived new connections and linkages between the actors.</p>

GOAL: INCLUSIVE MAKING

OUTCOMES OF RESEARCH	EXPECTED IMPACT PATHWAY	IDENTIFIED IMPACT
<p>Proof of concept for co-design & co-budgeting gender interventions</p> <p>Documented pilots for more inclusive making in different contexts (D3.2)</p> <p>Inspirational stories</p> <p>Guidelines for inclusive making</p>	<p>Easy to access concepts and guidelines for inclusive making enable the culture of inclusiveness to spread</p> <p>Facilitation of bottom-up attempts to solve the problems of gender bias in making empowers the underrepresented citizen groups in engaging (women, mothers, children, caretakers, non-binary people)</p>	<p>According to the feedback, the co-design process as well as the implementation of gender activities of WP3 enlarged participants' perspectives on 'gender aspects'</p> <p>WP3 interventions upskilled the participants by engaging women and children in making and creating new job opportunities</p>

<p>Webinar of women in engineering, presentation of WP3 results in several conferences</p> <p>Integrate Local Knowledge and Share How you Make Sessions in the the Critical Making mentoring sessions</p>	<p>Sharing inspirational narratives of marginalized groups in making globally empowers people to engage</p> <p>Guidelines for inclusive making can inform forthcoming EU projects in responsible and gender sensitive project design</p>	<p>Discussion of gender-inclusive making guidelines showed how much the guidelines triggered thinking about inclusiveness in the involved makerspaces. Makerspaces realized rooms for improvement in their own space. Individual participants understood what inclusiveness entails.</p> <p>Mentoring programme participants learned new ways to document and share their designs in a more inclusive and accessible ways.</p>
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CRITICAL MAKING EDUCATION

OUTCOMES OF RESEARCH	EXPECTED IMPACT PATHWAY	IDENTIFIED IMPACT
<p>Mapping of viabilities, challenges and possibilities for critical making education in Germany</p> <p>Critical Making in education guideline booklet</p> <p>Critical making torch kit</p> <p>Critical making manifesto</p>	<p>To integrate critical making into schools and education, it needs to fit into the existing curriculums and competence frameworks. Through experimenting and participatory learning, the capacity of teachers and educators to apply critical making methods develops.</p> <p>Easy to use learning kits make the approach more accessible in the future.</p>	<p>Many requests for the torch kits from maker spaces (e.g. Goodlab, HappyLab)</p> <p>Active workshop participation and enthusiastic feedback of workshop sessions.</p> <p>Excited feedback for the Critical Making manifesto and active contribution from stakeholders to its elaboration</p>

OPENNESS

OUTCOMES OF RESEARCH	EXPECTED IMPACT PATHWAY	IDENTIFIED IMPACT
<p>Critical Making mentoring programme</p> <p>Critical Making mentoring</p>	<p>The project provided easy to access materials for makers to learn from open hardware and open sharing practices and</p>	<p>Feedback in the Critical Making mentoring programme exit interviews about the increased skills in</p>

<p>youtube videos</p> <p>Critical Making mentoring programme project presentations in Wikifactory</p> <p>Joint writing of research paper between researchers and makers in WP 3 (D3.3.)</p>	<p>means. These materials are shared through existing networks of makers by GIG and Wikifactory and through workshops in maker events and Youtube to reach the broad audience of makers.</p> <p>Personal support by mentors and peers during mentoring programme improves the documentation and sharing skills of engaged makers who can in turn support their own communities.</p>	<p>documenting in a useful and more accessible ways (describing different phases, using videos etc.)</p> <p>Feedback in WP5 exit interviews that open sharing in Wikifactory has been inspiring and beneficial</p> <p>Feedback that several of the mentoring programme participants had learned new ways to build up the economic continuity of their projects from the beginning</p> <p>Open sharing was not limited to just copy or visuals, but in hosting on Wikifactory - sharing of CAD files that usually would have required a CAD software license that costs you 1,000s a year!</p> <p>Co-research practices between research team and makers has opened scientific practice to participants</p>
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AWARENESS RAISING

OUTCOMES OF RESEARCH	EXPECTED IMPACT PATHWAY	IDENTIFIED IMPACT
<p>Critical Making Responsibility Framework</p> <p>Critical Making tools for participatory and reflexive research</p> <p>Critical Making on-line Responsibility game for makers</p> <p>Critical making Zine</p>	<p>Active spreading of information on the idea and principles of critical making and practical guidelines for implementing critical making in different formats (research articles, blog posts, zine, online game, wikifactory contents, torch kit for children) etc makes critical making known for various audiences. Furthermore, the active collaboration and</p>	<p>Best paper award at FAB17 - there is clearly a need and recognition for GIM-RRR approach (CMRF)</p> <p>Feedback from makers in CMRF survey: they were excited to be able to answer the reflexive questions and deemed them useful for the future (e.g. for fundraising)</p>

<p>Special Issue on Critical Making</p> <p>Critical Making Reflection tool</p> <p>6 Scientific articles of openness, Critical Making Responsibility Framework, gender inclusion in making and critical making education</p> <p>Conference and workshop presentations introducing making and the project to academic audiences</p>	<p>partnering during the project lifetime with other EU funded projects and institutions will spread awareness of critical making. Snowballing among peers will further increase awareness.</p>	<p>Interest from Press to mention Critical Making in coverage around Wikifactory or Future of Manufacturing/Engineering</p> <p>The evaluation feedback indicates that the sustainability workshops in WP3 have raised the involved maker spaces' awareness for their own possibilities to become more inclusive and where they are not yet inclusive</p> <p>Saari et al, 2021 article on openness is the most read article of the special issue of Sustainability</p> <p>Making added to an open planetary wellbeing course in University of Jyväskylä, Finland after the conference presentation in YHYS colloquium in November 2022</p> <p>Enthusiastic response of the EU_SPRI 2023 conference audience on the introduction to critical making as a potential means towards socially responsible grassroots innovations.</p>
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Table 2: Critical Making impact pathways

4. CONTRIBUTION TO RRI DISCUSSIONS: EXPLORATION OF COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT RRI KEY

One of the core aims of our research project was to create an approach to RRI that can be applied with grass-roots initiatives and provide an insight on how grass-roots actors can measure the responsibility of their actions. The concept of RRI was developed a decade ago as a response to the need to deliberate the values embedded in the process of science and technology development and to provide a responsibility framework for research particularly in the context of European Union research and innovation funding. Following from that, the existing RRI frameworks such as MoRRI and SuperMoRRI provide tools to improve the governance of research in established research organisations. These tools are designed both for the purposes of self-governance of research performing organisations and for the use of external funding bodies (see e.g. Yaghmaei et al. 2022). In the beginning of the Critical Making project, we made an extensive literature review to explore how well the operationalisation of responsibility in these RRI debates resonates with the specific responsibility concerns emerging in the context of grassroots innovations. The results of this exercise are reported in D2.1. and two research articles (Sipos et al. 2022, Sipos & Åkerman 2023) and they clearly show the failure of mainstream RRI approaches to grasp innovation activities occurring outside established RDI organizations in citizen- and community-driven networks. RRI has also been accused of being Euro-centric and unable to recognize the frugal and grassroots innovations arising in the Global South.

To address the identified gap in RRI, we explored what the four RRI capacities (anticipation, reflection, inclusiveness, responsiveness) could mean when studied through the lenses of grassroots innovation studies with a focus on the context, framings, spaces & strategies and pathways of grassroots innovation movement and communities (Critical Making Responsibility Framework (CMRF), see *ibid.*). As a result of this exploration, we recognized that there is one central RRI dimension missing in the established set of RRI keys (gender, public engagement, ethics, science education, open access and governance). This dimension is a functioning

community. This result was also validated within several co-creation workshops organised by WP2 for the development of the CMRF. Therefore, we added a new dimension, *community empowerment*, to the RRI dimensions followed in our project and decided to investigate how it could be turned into a measurable new RRI key. This far we had to base our work on previous literature. To address the topic in our own evaluation, we identified the following key aspects as central and designed WP specific evaluation frames so that we could measure these during the case interventions:

- creation of joyful experiences
- generation of long-term participation for community actions
- creation of supportive community
- support of open sharing and knowledge exchange within the community

To get feedback for the idea of a new RRI key, we presented our approach in the EU_SPRI conference in June 2022 in an RRI evaluation working group (Saari, Åkerman, Kieslinger & Sipos 2022). The idea got interested response and the lack of community aspects in RRI discussions was agreed by working group colleagues. However, many commentators pointed at the mismatch between the level of analysing RRI from the point of view of research governance on one hand and from the perspective of particular research projects or grassroots innovation projects. With the latter one, community empowerment is definitely central while activities situate in particular communities whereas at the level of organizations or research programmes and agendas, the relevant communities are more difficult to define. Furthermore, some commentators also pointed out the contestations around the idea that short term research or innovation, particularly if conducted by an outsider to a community could or should empower communities and reaminded about the risk of neocolonial attitude with the wording of empowerment.

After the EU_SPRI conference, we decided to investigate in a more data driven way about the meaning of community in making during the entry and exit interviews of the Critical Making mentoring programme. We asked the interviewees to describe how they aim to respond to the needs of their communities with their projects, what kinds of barriers and tensions related to community relations they have encountered during the project and how and whom of their communities they have aimed to engage in their projects. Furthermore, we probed discussion about the role of the community of makers for their projects. Based on the data

collected during the entry and exit interviews and a review of community empowerment literature (e.g. Zimmerman 2000; Kasmel & Andersen 2011; Laverack 2001), we elaborated the dimensions of community empowerment and presented the results in the EU_SPRI Conference Social Innovations full paper research Track in June 2023. In that conference paper, we identified the following dimensions particularly important for maker projects of the Global South in terms of community empowerment (Saari, Åkerman & Kieslinger 2023, full paper submitted for the conference - article in progress, see slides attached):

- Learning creative use of resources under scarcity (responding to the needs of community)
- Increasing situational awareness (recognizing the patterns that create disadvantages)
- Learning to manage community relations and relations to broader society
- Access to new skills and knowledge for the disadvantaged citizen groups
- Support of sharing and knowledge exchange

All the above issues came out in the interviews and relate to the role of maker projects and global maker community in *empowering the local* communities and individuals engaged with the project. Often, there is a distinction made in the literature between this approach and the notion of *empowered communities* focusing on identifying how and in which terms communities can challenge the existing societal structure (e.g. Zimmerman 2000). Our data did not provide tools for studying communities from this perspective.

Due to the short project schedule, we were unfortunately not able to elaborate the concept of new RRI key as far as we would have wanted, as we only received our empirical data in the mid-March 2023. We will continue elaborating our research paper presented in the EU_SPRI 2023 conference to be submitted in September 2023 for publication. Due to the changes in the EU level RRI debates following from the decision to integrate the RRI and public engagement as overarching issues in the new Horizon programme, we however made a decision to elaborate the evaluation of community empowerment impacts of projects in a more focused way to contribute for the discussions of responsibility of community-driven open innovations rather than to develop an aggregate level RRI key.

5. SDG IMPACTS OF THE PROJECT

Critical Making project was also committed to contribute to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG:s). These include a set of 17 goals that cover social, economic and environmental aspects of sustainability. As the original goals are designed for national level, they need to be adapted to evaluate a single project, as we elaborated in the Evaluation Framework D6.1. In that framework, we have also identified the five most important SDG:s for the project. As the project progressed and the focus clarified, we decided to drop the SDG 8 from the list because economic growth was not a strong focus on any of the activities even though livelihood and need to generate income was present in some activities. For example, in the mentoring programme of WP5, some entrepreneurial makers were participating and received guidance on building an economically sustainable and profitable business model. In addition, we realised that project contributes to SDG 17, Partnerships for the goals. Creating global networks and building fruitful, impact focused connections between makers from different parts of the world as well as inside communities was important in several actions of the Critical Making project. The final selected SDGs are introduced in the figure 9 below.

Figure 9: The most important SDG's for Critical Making project.

As the main project activities, outcomes and impacts are already introduced in the previous sections, we present in the following only a short summary of the most important actions taken for each of the most important SDGs.

SDG 4 - Quality education

Contributing to developing better education practices was one of the three main focuses of Critical Making, especially targeted in WP4. This work package focused on developing educational making. It produced a torch light kit that is easy to assemble and allows children to learn basics of electronics with simple materials. In addition, a guideline of Critical Making education was produced to be disseminated into schools and makerspaces, promoting inclusive, responsive and educational making. This case action focused specifically in Germany, but many aspects of it are disseminated also elsewhere, e.g. the Critical Making Manifesto.

SDG 5 - Gender equality

Gender equality was another focus of Critical Making, focused especially on WP3. The work package focused on raising awareness of gender diversity in making. For this purpose, inspirational stories of women and non-binary persons in making were published in the project website. It also supported development of context-specific care-taker inclusive makerspace concepts that allow participation also with children. A guideline to inclusive making was also published, and local female makers were supported in South-Sudan and Cameroon. All of these activities, with the exception of writing the inspirational stories which also started as an idea from the community, were community-led, thus laying a good ground for continuation of new practices.

SDG 9 - Industry, innovation and infrastructure

Critical Making aimed at supporting more sustainable, locally distributed manufacturing models. One example of this is a hand sanitizer workshops arranged in South-Sudan. The aim was to support local female brewers producing hand-sanitizers during the pandemic by helping them create the social space for alcohol brewing inside the community as well as enhance their safety. Another example of supporting innovation and new infrastructures is the mentoring programme, where many of the participating projects focused on creating new models of local production. In the community creation of the mentoring programme, innovation related knowledge exchange and creation of new networks were in focus.

SDG 10 - Reduced inequalities

Critical Making was working towards more equal opportunities, for example in taking part in manufacturing and design activities. For example, the guideline on inclusive making does focus on different groups, including those with disabilities or limited financial resources. The reflection tool and online game created in the project also guide the user to reflect on these things. In the Critical Making mentoring programme, especially people in vulnerable situations were reached. They were supported in their efforts to create more opportunities for local youth, women and people living in refugee camps, for example.

SDG 12 - Responsible consumption and production

Making, especially with a critical mindset, has substantial potential in adding to more responsible consumption and production. In WP4, where youth and children were targeted, awareness of production methods and supply chains was supported in workshops arranged for children and their parents. Through the Critical Making mentoring programme of WP5 and the gender actions of WP3 responsible small-scale production methods were also supported. Through disseminating openly, e.g. by publishing the mentoring sessions on Youtube and promoting sustainable projects on Wikifactory, public awareness of these good practices is also created.

SDG 17 - Partnerships for the goals

The Critical Making project did make continuous efforts to create new ties and networks that cover different geographic areas. New networks that included makers from both the Global South and the Global North were created in the mentoring programme, where networking played a crucial part. The project also focused on strengthening partnerships inside communities, for example by working with the female brewers in South-Sudan by supporting their goal of persuading the local religious leaders to approve their activities of alcohol-brewing for the purpose of producing hand-sanitizers.

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ANNEX. COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT CONFERENCE SLIDES

Critical Making
rp15 | BUN-5/5
Leading change

Making for a more just transition: Global maker movement and its potential for societal changes

Hanna Saari
VTT

Wikifactory | ZSI | gig GLOBAL INNOVATION GATHERING | VTT | TU

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Introducing Critical Making project

Critical Thinking + Making
= Critical Making

- ❖ Participatory action research
- ❖ Three focus areas: 1) gender, 2) youth and 3) **Openness**

SHO

Our study

- Group interviews with 15 participants of Critical Making mentoring programme
- Random groups of 2-5 participants
- Focus on communities
- Mostly experienced, critical makers

*Europe+Iraq

How does community empowerment appear in maker communities, especially in areas suffering from resource scarcity?

Starting points to our analysis

- Previous literature emphasises the empowering potential of the maker movement – giving people more tools for technological agency and offering opportunities for entrepreneurship (e.g. Tanenbaum et al. 2013; Dreesen, Schepers & Laen 2016)
- Empowerment consists of many, partly interrelated aspects, such as:
 - ❖ *Skills and knowledge*
 - ❖ *Mental models and psychological sense of control*
 - ❖ *Inclusive organizational structures*
 - ❖ *Links between organizations*
 - ❖ *Resources and ability to utilize them*

See e.g.: Zimmerman 2000; Kasmel & Andersen 2011; Laverack 2001

Areas of desired impact

	nutrition	health	safety	education & livelihood	environment	access to electricity	community
Africa	1	4		3	1	1	
South-America	1			1			
Europe (& Iraq)	1		1				1
TOTAL	3	4	1	4	1	1	1

Target groups

- Most projects aim at empowering some previously disempowered groups, such as:
 - Women and girls (6)
 - Refugees (6)
 - Youth and children (5)

Goals of community empowerment

	linkages	skills	knowledge	representation	resources	organizational structures	joyful experiences
Africa		6	2	2	7	1	
South-America		2	1			1	1
Europe (& Iraq)	1			1			1
TOTAL	1	8	3	3	7	2	2

Approaches to economic side of projects

Sustaining the activities

- ❖ Money needed for materials
- ❖ Paying for employees
- ❖ Sell one - donate one - business logic

Economic empowerment

- ❖ Empowering women to be economically independent
- ❖ Offering training for youth so they can find employment
- ❖ Creating a viable business

Differences between the Global South and Global North - complementing vs. disrupting the system

Concluding

- The global maker movement can offer an online platform for community development arising from the grassroots
- In resource scarce environments the focus of maker initiatives seems to be in empowering community members while political efforts are left on the background
- ***In order for a truly just green transition, actors in the Global South trying to ensure the very basic needs of their communities should be supported - through supporting the community empowerment initiatives through offering skills, knowledge and resources.***

Literature

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**The growing role of globally connected,
locally acting maker communities for
societal change:
Insights from the Global South**

Hanna Saari, Maria Åkerman, Barbara Kieslinger
EU_SPRI Conference
15.05.2023

Critical Making project 2021-2023

Research objective

Objective: Critically study the innovation processes in the maker movement with regards to social responsibility, especially in relation to gender, openness, recruitment of young people and more generally, their social responsibility

Wikifactory

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101006285

Context

What is *making*?

(Doyle 2013)

Previous literature emphasises the empowering potential of the maker movement – giving people more tools for technological agency and offering opportunities for entrepreneurship (e.g. Tanenbaum et al. 2013; Dressen, Schepers & Leen 2016)

→ BUT, claims of technocentrism, gender bias, exclusive practices..

How do maker communities empower people in the communities suffering from resource scarcity?

We study maker communities more as *empowering the individuals* to find better ways to cope with their living realities rather than *empowered communities* aiming at societal or political changes.

MENTORING PROGRAMME FOR PROMOTING IMPACT 6 OPENNESS IN MAKING

18 participants from Africa, South America & Europe

The context for the projects in the Global South:

- Refugee camps
- Small villages in rural Africa
- Low income neighbourhoods in Latin America

Critical Making mentoring programme

How can you advance your product innovation based on openness and critical thinking?

We are inviting makers & innovators globally to take part in the journey towards shaping a sustainable future of making.

All mentoring sessions will take place online, so you can participate from anywhere in the world.

meet the teachers

Saad Chinyere
Make things that make sense
In the first workshop, the general sense of maker projects will be considered. What are the problems you are trying to tackle with your making? How to consider what's already been made? What are the opportunities?

Emilia Vella
Share how you make it
In the second workshop of the series, questions of 'giving and receiving' of ideas are considered. Sharing is not a simple task, if you wish for others to be able to make and sense what you have made.

Arunith Panch
Include ecosystem services
The third workshop of the series focuses on the environment you are working in.

Georgina Nicolau
Integrate local knowledge
In this workshop, you will learn about different solutions that could be found through co-design or other human-centred design practices where the local knowledge beyond your make-space can be utilized.

Behar Kumar
Build for continuity
The last workshop of the series focuses on financial questions to help to make your making financially sustainable. In this workshop, you will get tools to build a self-sustaining, continuous making practice.

Programme Outline

- First Deadline for applications: May 20th
- Second Deadline for applications: May 25th
- Entry interview: August
- Workshop series: August to December
- Exit interview: January
- Demo Week: January

criticalmaking.eu

SHO

Our data

- Entry & exit Group interviews with 15 participants of Critical Making mentoring programme
- Random groups of 2-5 participants
- Focus on communities & impact

Critical Making mentoring programme

EXAMPLES OF MENTORING PROGRAMME PROJECTS

Irrigation Kit

A gravity-fed modular irrigation kit- a sim...
Created by: [Critical Making](#)

Virando Jogo

Jogos educativos feitos em madeira e lac...
Created by: [Critical Making](#)

AUTO WATER DISPENSER

This project is based on an infrared (IR) s...
Created by: [Critical Making](#)

3D Printed Wireless Digital Stethoscope

Digital Stethoscope [CM]

My current project is about a Digital Wirel...
Created by: [Critical Making](#)

STEM : Water Filter Kit

This project promotes STEM education i...

DIY ultra bass amplifier

DIY Audio Ultra Bass Amplifier:DIY audio ...
Created by: [Critical Making](#)

Empowering factors

Creative use of resources under scarcity

"--- when it's completed, we want the moms to be able to sell of the band, so that they can have income for themselves also, so that they are not stuck in relationship or with problems getting the right nutrition, for the baby to grow healthy and also for themselves and accessing health care

Increasing situational awareness

This is in order to help them find solutions to their contextual challenges that put them at a disadvantage

Learning to manage community relations and relations with wider society

Hard time for navigating the particular ecosystems of health and data privacy administration to elaborate the innovation

There are things that they have handed down from generations — and it is so entrenched in their minds that it is a challenge sometimes to convince people otherwise because they also do it out of respect for the older generation, and sometimes they are forced to listen

Access to new skills and knowledge for the disadvantaged citizen groups

So she is trying to look at training the women, so they get the knowledge and also get the confidence to do something. Because they have a mentality in her community of thinking that women are still backward, women can not do this and that. So she is trying to advocate for them to join the hardware thing

Sharing

it's different from every community, but we all have similar challenges across the world

- Empowerment consists of many, partly interrelated aspects, such as:
 - ❖ *Skills and knowledge*
 - ❖ *Mental models and psychological sense of control*
 - ❖ *Inclusive organizational structures*
 - ❖ *Links between organizations*
 - ❖ *Resources and ability to utilize them*

See e.g.: Zimmerman 2000; Kasmel & Andersen 2011; Laverack 2001

THE WAYS IN WHICH
MAKER COMMUNITIES
OFFERED NOVEL
OPPORTUNITIES AND
REORGANISED SOCIAL
RELATIONS

Concluding remarks:

- Because maker communities act bottom-up and are integral parts of the local communities they have the ability to identify the needs of the communities and engage often underrepresented citizen groups in grassroots innovations
- Yet, they are globally connected, which enables the circulation of innovations, designs and solutions from one place to another
- But how much they can challenge the existing paradigm of production and consumption? - Policy advocacy?

Thanks!

The Critical Making Consortium
<https://criticalmaking.eu/>

Credits: This presentation could contain elements from Slidesgo, Flaticon & Freepik.

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